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A cell death program.

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Discovery and design of novel cancer therapeutics will be augmented by development of a comprehensive transcriptional readout of survival programs functioning in human cells undergoing cell death. We describe here a cell death program for use in cancer discovery research that incorporates key components of the apoptotic, necroptotic, and ferroptotic cell death pathways. The complete program viewed as an intergrated readout will allow enhanced study of small molecules and natural products that provide information regarding specific survival signals engaged by the chemotherapeutic as well as important data that illustrate kinetics of cell death activation in a dynamic fashion.